

Prospects for Increasing Population Income

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Abstract: *The article discusses the relevance of increasing population income, with a particular focus on the state policy implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure employment. It also analyzes the measures undertaken in Kashkadarya region to secure employment and the outcomes of these efforts. Additionally, proposals and recommendations have been developed to ensure employment in the regions.*

Keywords: *employment, population, unemployment, income, sector, average income, budget, principle.*

Introduction.

The level of income is one of the key factors ensuring the socio-economic stability and development of any society. Increasing household incomes not only improves individual well-being but also contributes to the overall economic growth of the country. The growing global economic volatility and widening social inequality underline the relevance of this topic today.

First and foremost, an increase in income improves the standard of living for the population. When people's basic needs are met, they begin to think about fulfilling higher-level needs. For instance, a family with higher income invests more in the education of their children, which in turn enhances the development of the nation's human capital. Additionally, rising incomes boost consumer purchasing power, which drives the development of domestic markets.

Secondly, increasing household incomes is essential for reducing economic inequality. In today's world, high levels of poverty are not only a personal issue but also a threat to social stability. A fair distribution of income helps maintain social balance within society and prevents potential social tensions.

Thirdly, the growth of household incomes strengthens the economic potential of the state. Higher incomes expand the tax base, which brings additional revenue to the state budget. Consequently, the government can allocate more funds to social and infrastructure projects. This, in turn, creates jobs and accelerates economic growth.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the adoption of the Presidential Decree titled “On measures to increase youth income and ensure employment by allocating land to young people, as well as to develop new land areas”¹ underscores the state's commitment to addressing key policy objectives. These include increasing the cultivation of food crops through the efficient use of land and water resources in agriculture, ensuring the employment of the population, including youth, and boosting their income levels.

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PD-153 dated April 5, 2024, “On measures to increase youth incomes and ensure employment through land allocation, as well as the development of new land areas”.

One of the effective strategies for increasing income is supporting small and private entrepreneurship. This sector plays a crucial role in ensuring employment and raising household incomes. Simultaneously, reforms aimed at enhancing labor productivity in the production and service sectors contribute to the overall income levels of the population.

Additionally, education and professional training are of great importance in boosting incomes. Highly skilled specialists are in high demand in the labor market and can achieve higher earnings. In this regard, government initiatives to invest in educational and retraining programs play a vital role. Specifically, in our country, it is essential to elevate the quality of higher education to a new level and establish a system for preparing highly qualified professionals who can contribute to the sustainable development of the social sector and economic industries and secure a strong position in the labor market².

Research methodology.

In the research, extensive use was made of statistical observation, compilation, grouping, and analysis through tables and graphs. Additionally, methods such as analysis, synthesis, induction, and deduction were employed.

Literature analysis.

The issue of increasing household incomes remains one of the most pressing topics in economic theory and applied research. In this regard, Samuelson and Nordhaus conducted extensive studies and provided theoretical foundations on the formation, distribution, and consumption impact of economic incomes in their renowned book, *Economics*. They emphasized that the unequal distribution of incomes can lead to social and economic tensions, striving to substantiate this phenomenon³.

Atkinson proposed his theoretical views on income inequality and its impact on economic development, arguing that income inequality reduces economic efficiency and leads to issues of social justice within society⁴.

Becker, in his theory of *Human Capital*, emphasized that investing in human capital (through education, professional training, and healthcare) is crucial for increasing incomes⁵.

Among Uzbek researchers, A.K.Abdurakhmonov⁶ has researched ways to increase population income through structural reforms in the labor market. Similarly, A.A.Rakhmatov⁷ has conducted scientific studies on increasing the population's income while maintaining sustainable economic development, encouraging the socially vulnerable segments of the population to transition into economically active groups and analyzing the proportion of low-income individuals within the country's population.

Analysis and results.

² Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PD-5847 dated October 8, 2019, "On approval of the concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030".

³ Samuelson, P. A., & Nordhaus, W. D. (1999). *Economics*. McGraw-Hill. 744 pages.

⁴ Atkinson, A. B. (2015). *Inequality: What Can Be Done?* Harvard University Press. 384 pages.

⁵ Becker, G. S. (1993). *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education* (3rd ed.). University of Chicago Press. 237 pages.

⁶ Абдурахмонов К.Х. (2004). "Меҳнат иқтисодиёти (назария ва амалиёт)". Тошкент- "Меҳнат", 18-бет.

⁷ РАХМАТОВ, А. (2023). АҲОЛИ ДАРОМАДЛАРИНИ ОШИРИШ ВА КАМБАҒАЛЛИКНИ ҚИСҚАРТИРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ. *Journal of Fundamental Studies*, 1(1), 71-75.

In the republic, impactful measures are being implemented annually to ensure employment through the execution of approved programs. These include improving mechanisms for placing individuals in vacant and quota-based jobs and promoting effective forms of self-employment.

Several regulatory and legal documents have been adopted to encourage the labor activity and entrepreneurial initiatives of the population, ensure employment for socially vulnerable groups and enhance access to quality and efficiency of state employment services.

Despite these efforts, the labor market in certain regions remains highly strained. Challenges persist in creating permanent jobs, ensuring employment for youth, women and members of low-income families especially in rural areas and addressing issues related to the regulation of external labor migration processes⁸.

To enhance the reliability of our research, we analyzed the socio-economic indicators of the Kashkadarya region.

Kashkadarya region was established on november 1, 1924. It borders Bukhara region to the northwest, Surkhandarya region to the southeast, Turkmenistan to the south and west, Tajikistan to the east and Samarkand region to the northeast.

The region primarily encompasses the Kashkadarya depression, surrounded by the Zarafshan and Hissar mountain ranges to the north, east and southeast. The area between the mountains and plains is occupied by foothills. A significant part of the plain in the west is composed of the Karshi desert, which merges with the Sandikli and Kyzylkum deserts. The total area is 28,600 km², with a population of 3,408,300 people.

The region includes 2 cities subordinate to the region, 12 district centers, 14 districts, 117 townships, 819 mahalla citizens' assemblies, and 1,042 residential settlements.

The climate is continental, with relatively mild winters. Summers are long (155–160 days), hot, and dry. The average temperature in january ranges from 0.2°C to 1.9°C, while in july it ranges from 28°C to 29.5°C. The highest recorded temperature is 45°C. The vegetation period lasts up to 290–300 days in the plains.

The regional center is Karshi city, one of the major cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The city is located 384 meters above sea level.

The population primarily consists of Uzbeks (92.9%), along with Tajiks, Turkmens, Russians, Kazakhs, Ukrainians, Azerbaijanis, Koreans, Kyrgyz, Turks, Belarusians, Tatars and representatives of other ethnic groups. The average population density is 109.0 people per km². The urban population is 1.46 million, while the rural population is 1.9483 million.

The region is a major repository of natural resources in Uzbekistan. Kashkadarya contributes 70% of the country's natural gas production, 78% of its oil, 13% of its grain, and 14% of its cotton. Over the past five years, the gross regional product has doubled. Major industrial facilities include the Talimarjan thermal power plant, "Uzbekistan GTL" LLC, Muborak gas processing plant, Shurtan gas chemical complex and the Kukdumalak oil field.

In addition, the region contains reserves of 33.4 million tons of glass raw materials, 1,539 million tons of mineral salts, 279.8 million tons of cement raw materials, 11.1 million tons of limestone for

⁸ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PD-3856 dated july 14, 2018, "On improving and enhancing the efficiency of efforts to ensure population employment".

calcination, 18.6 million cubic meters of sand and gravel materials, 68.7 million tons of gypsum and anhydrite, and 3.4 million cubic meters of clay for ceramics.

Table 1. Per capita income indicators⁹

(Thousand sum)

№	Names of cities and districts	Average income of the population	including,			Average expenditure of the population
			From budgetary funds	From the non-governmental sector (specifically from entrepreneurship)	From other sources	
	Total:	13 204	8 100	11 200	15 113	11 300
1	Karshi city	14 120	9 150	12 400	14880	12708
2	Shakhrisabz city	13 195	8 090	12 100	14520	11876
	districts:					
3	Guzar	12 150	7 020	10 800	12960	10935
4	Dehkanabad	11 800	6 700	10 200	12240	10620
5	Kamashi	12 090	7 170	10 700	12840	10881
6	Karshi	12 860	7 300	10 920	13104	11574
7	Koson	13 100	7 600	11 100	13320	11790
8	Kitob	12 900	7 760	11 040	13248	11610
9	Mirishkor	11 920	6 800	10 300	12360	10728
10	Muborak	12 400	7 100	10 450	12540	11160
11	Nishon	12 100	7 280	10 650	12780	10890
12	Kasbi	12 520	7 600	10 200	12240	11268
13	Kukdala	10 600	6 900	10 125	12150	9540
14	Chiroqchi	12 320	7 420	10 920	13104	11088
15	Shakhrisabz	12 100	7 900	10 780	12936	10890
16	Yakkabog	12 700	7 800	10 950	13140	11430

As of January 1, 2024, the labor resources in the region amount to 1,825,300 individuals, of whom 1,336,159 are classified as economically active. Out of these, 1,212,816 individuals are employed across various economic sectors. Employment distribution is as follows: 25% in agriculture, 15% in industry, 16% in trade, 8% in construction, 7% in transportation and storage, 6% in education, 4% in forestry, and 11% in other sectors.

The region has significant potential for creating new job opportunities. If these opportunities are utilized effectively and based on scientific principles, it is possible to ensure employment for all labor resources.

⁹ www.qashstat.uz.

Figure 1. Key principles in the field of employment¹⁰.

A number of initiatives are being implemented to ensure employment, involve vulnerable populations in labor activities, and provide social protection for unemployed citizens. Decrees and resolutions adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as videoconference meetings, have outlined priority tasks aimed at creating new jobs, increasing household incomes, and reducing poverty. Specifically, measures are being taken to ensure the employment of 5 million people this year, including the creation of 2 million permanent jobs¹¹.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Our research has primarily revealed that a significant portion of the economically active population in the labor market of our country is unemployed, and the majority of those employed are concentrated in the agricultural sector. These realities do not align with the requirements of the modern market economy. In our view, to increase the population's income, it is necessary to accelerate state reforms in the following areas:

¹⁰ O‘zbekiston Respublikasining 20.10.2020 yildagi “Aholi bandligi to‘g‘risida” O‘RQ-642-son Qonuni.

¹¹ Joint Resolution No. 2980-IV of the Legislative Chamber and Senate Councils of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated february 21, 2023, “On enhancing the effectiveness of parliamentary oversight over efforts to ensure population employment in regions”.

- continuously updating modern technologies, innovations, and professional training programs for employees in the activities of economic entities to improve labor productivity;
- creating new job opportunities, expanding remote work capabilities, and developing new income sources through the widespread use of digital technologies in the economy;
- promoting entrepreneurship development in regions through the use of tax incentives and financial support mechanisms;
- considering that a significant portion of the population is engaged in agriculture, it is essential to develop agricultural infrastructure and expand investment opportunities in this sector.

Measures aimed at increasing population income require a comprehensive and systematic approach. Ensuring that state policies are directed toward achieving economic stability, fostering cooperation with the private sector, and broadening the economic opportunities for the population is crucial. The steady growth of income serves as a solid foundation for ensuring social justice and driving economic development.

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